

www.arseam.com

Impact Factor: 3.43

Cite this paper as : Ms. Priyanka & Pramod Gupta (2017), “An Analysis of Family Business Strategy and Growth in Indian Scenario”, International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management, ISSN: 2348 –3954 (online) ISSN: 2349 –2546 (print), Volume 5,(Issue9, Sep-2017), pp 10-21

An Analysis of Family Business Strategy and Growth in Indian Scenario

Ms. Priyanka

Research Scholar

Department of Management Studies,
Sunrise University, Alwar, Raj. India

Dr. Pramod Gupta

Associate Professor

Department of Management Studies,
Sunrise University, Alwar, Raj. India

ABSTRACT

In India the majority of businesses are in the dominant control of the families. It is estimated that 90% of the business in India is controlled by families. From 'Mom and Pop' Kirana stores to large conglomerates and SME's one finds family run businesses. Most of the big corporate business houses like Tatas, Ambanis, Birlas, Godrej, Wadias, Munjals, Mahindra, Thapars, Mittals, Shaparji Paollonji, Jindals, Adanis, Anil Aggarwal – Vedanta, Bajaj, Ruias, Ranbaxy, Times of India and many more are all controlled by families. The role of family and the family patriarch is quite important in India.

There are many families who have separated and partitioned. Some such families have succeeded and the separated branches have also grown big, while in some cases the branches which have separated or the business as a whole have failed or collapsed. There are mixed reports as and when the family separate.

Key –Words: Multi-generational dimension, FDI, Professional management, EVA.

Introduction:

A **family business** is a commercial organization in which decision-making is influenced by multiple generations of a family—related by blood or marriage. They are closely identified with the firm through leadership or ownership. Owner-manager entrepreneurial firms are not considered to be family businesses because they lack the multi-generational dimension and family influence that create the unique dynamics and relationships of family businesses.

In India traditionally the family business is the norm. The trend continues. However, there are certain business houses where the professional teams are taking over to run the empires. These cases are also multiplying as the wealth is growing at different levels.

The recent cases are of Tata Group where a serious head hunting programme was done to find a successor to Mr. Ratan Tata. Mr. Mistry was appointed to head the Tata Group. The famous IT Company Infosys has seen the change at the top level when Mr. Narayan Murthy has been successful in appointing the well-known professional personality Mr. Vishal Sikka to head the business founded by him.

Family business remains the norm for a large section of society in India and is not going to fade away. There are obviously going to be exceptions depending upon the size and nature of business.

Objectives:

- To study the importance of Family Business in India.
- To study the strengths and Opportunities of Indian Family Business.
- To anticipate the problems and challenges faced by Indian Family Business.

If the family businesses are planned properly and the family plans professionally on their investment companies and business operating companies the same shall continue to be a successful business model. In a growing economy and in view of the global reach family businesses are undergoing changes and the element of professional management and professional participation is increasing which is the key to a successful business model. Today the young generation of each family is well educated, exposed to global standards and situations and trained for professional management which all lays down a robust foundation for future stability and growth.

What are the key challenges facing family firms in India?

Inter family disputes, the patriarch acting as a control freak, lack of professional management and professional participation, absence of family constitution on running of business and handling family wealth, lack of written understanding to address any conflict, lack of communication amongst the family members, unsound and unfair policies for the employees, lack of quality controls and to keep pace with the modern techniques and advancements are the key challenges to any family firms in India.

Are family firms changing the way they are managed/governed?

The family firms are certainly changing the way they are managed and governed. The decision making ability in a family run business is high, however, to manage the business professionally and to get the right talent to run the business is always a challenge in even large business and corporate houses.

There are many business houses where the trend is changing especially where the young generation is educated and educated well in India and overseas, and the new generation realises the value which can be added by the right governance structure, right talent and right delegation. The new generation is also keen to have alliances and joint venture in India and overseas. The world is flat and global opportunities are available by way of FDI, JVs, and equity participation which is being experienced and realised by the youth and the new generation.

Furthermore, the ideas of listing the company in India and/or overseas and creating value are also on the wish list and dream of the new generation. It can be noticed that large families are shrinking to unit families; and families today are willing to give chance to next generation.

The families are increasingly retaining professionals to run the businesses and are also interested in settling down the succession related issues relating to their personal assets as well as running of business in a professional manner.

That the environment of family business in India has significantly changed over the period is indicated as follows:

Earlier	Presently
(a) Business as family	(a) Family as business
(b) Family wealth and prosperity	(b) Shareholders' value and prosperity
(c) Growth strategies	(c) Economic Value Added (EVA)
(d) Expansion and diversification	(d) Core and competitive competencies
(e) Family succession planning for next generation	(e) Planning for attraction and retention of professionals

Is succession planning a big issue?

Succession Planning is a big issue today inter alia for the following reasons:

- Increase in wealth and also increase in the number of HNIs and UHNIs. There is a noticeable increase in wealthy Indians and with wealth comes a serious requirement to plan the succession so that the wealth is preserved and not destroyed.
- Most of the business houses are often exposed to local and overseas liabilities owing to their borrowings or trade related activities. This compels them to plan for asset protection trust in good times when the creation of such a trust and transfer of the assets to such a trust is not perceived as a fraudulent transfer. This requires an early and matured planning.
- Wealthy Indians have assets in India and overseas. Today the succession planning is not required only for Indian based assets; it is also important and imperative in the global context.
- The Indians living in USA or the NRI community or persons of Indian origin living in USA and inheriting assets in India are potentially exposed to global taxation and have to plan for their estate and succession accordingly.
- Nuclear families have a need for succession planning and services around succession planning as people want to know how to do their Will and whom to appoint as the Executor and with whom to keep the safe custody of Will.
- There is a possibility of the introduction of Estate Duty again and if this happens all concerned will have to do the succession planning in a proper way to ensure smooth succession which is economical as well.

How do families in India plan and manage succession?

The practice and philosophy is different for each family depending upon size of the family, the family wealth, their needs and the nature of business or professional activity. There is no uniform practice on this.

Most of the families are happy and content to do their Wills and to declare their wishes on inheritance in their Wills. The families with substantial wealth or special needs or for asset protection from creditors in worst case scenario prefer to prepare their Trusts and do the planning accordingly.

Increasingly families are looking for a mixed structure which encompasses Will and Trust both to plan the succession for themselves and their next generations.

Large business houses as well as large families are increasing taking professional help to write the Family Constitution and to put right legal structures in place so that one member or one set of family members are not in a position to create any embarrassment or legal disputes or disadvantageous situation for the family.

One such example is where shareholding of the company is with multiple family members. To check any mischief it is an increasing trend that instead of holding the shares in individual names, who may transfer the shareholdings, either the shareholdings are kept in a Trust or some kind of escrow mechanism so that the other family members may have the right of first refusal in the event of sale of shares by one family member or one branch of family. All these are serious issues and increasingly the professional help is sought by families to balance such conflicts or potential disputes.

Moreover, a large and growing number of new family groups have appeared on the corporate landscape in the 1990s. Many of these are jostling with the old guard for a leadership position. Fresh blood such as the Nambiaris (BPL), the Guptas (Lloyds Steel), the Jindals (Jindal Strips), the Oswals (OWM and Vardhman), the Singhs

(Ranbaxy), the Shahras (Ruchi Soya), the Mehtas (Torrent), the Lohias (Indo Rama), the Dhoots (Videocon), and the Premjis (Wipro) have elbowed out former stalwarts such as the Dalmias, the Modis, and the Walchands. Most of these new groups grew steadily in the 1980s but came into prominence in the 1990s.

The robustness of the new groups, combined with the unmistakable vitality in at least a dozen of the older established ones, is proof enough that family business in India is not just alive, but kicking. Their main strength lies in understanding the environment that they operate in. This is borne out by a BT-Gallup MBA study which polled a sample of 363 respondents, comprising consultants and academicians (54), CEOs and senior managers (48), middle managers (77), B-School students (110), brokers (48), and executives in banks and financial institutions (FIs, 26), in Ahmedabad, Bangalore, Calcutta, Chennai, Delhi, and Mumbai. According to the study, the two biggest strengths of Indian business families are their understanding of the Indian environment, and image. The CEOs and senior managers perceived the first factor as the biggest plus, followed by political savvy. On the other hand, 38 per cent of the middle managers plumped for image followed by an understanding of the environment.

SWOT Analysis of Indian Family Business:

STRENGTHS

A family business offers the following advantages:

- One of the popular misconceptions about family businesses is that they are unable to adapt easily to increasing competitiveness and technological progress. The reality is that family businesses frequently have the advantage of entrepreneurial spirit, flexibility, and opportunism.

- It is believed by some that family firms are —too soft and rarely reach their potential. The reality is that family businesses actually outperform public companies. Oftentimes, the marketplace forces public companies to make short-term decisions, whereas a family business has the advantage of having more freedom to make its decisions. Family businesses can adapt to market fluctuations more easily because they can afford to be patient. They have common goals, shared values, and a commitment to brand building.

- Family-owned businesses are often seen as ideal because family members form a —grounded and loyal foundation for the company, and family members tend to exhibit more dedication to their common goals. —Having a certain level of intimacy among the owners of a business can help bring about familiarity with the company and having family members around provides a built-in support system that should ensure teamwork and solidarity.

- The culture of a family business is very different from that of a company you will find on Wall Street.

—Family businesses frequently take a very long-term point of view. They’ll make investments that they don’t expect to pay off for 5 or 15 or 25 years...Culture in a family business is more frequently based on very personal and emotional values. It’s stronger because there are deeper roots and closer connections to the history of the company.

- Family businesses are becoming more and more attractive to undergraduate business students who face a bleak job and salary outlook for new grads. These undergrads are choosing to return to their family businesses directly after graduation instead of trying to find a job in corporate America or on Wall Street.
- There is a common misperception that family businesses are less professional and rigorous in their behavior because of the relational nature of the businesses. However, like all other businesses, family businesses face global competition and rapidly changing markets. This creates more pressure on those who join to make sure that they produce. —This emphasis on professionalism has made family businesses both more daunting and more attractive—and has created new interest in them, from family members, outsiders, and business school students.
- Many family-owned businesses tend to be stable and optimistic, even when economic times are uncertain. They seem to be better able to weather economic difficulties and stabilize the economy than their nonfamily counterparts. However, this is a function of the industry and the size of the business.
- In general, family businesses feel that they are stronger because family members are involved in their activities. Family owners believe that their family members can be trusted, will work harder, and care more. This can help create competitive advantage in the marketplace.
- Family businesses may be more open to flexible or part-time schedules or choosing your hours. This presents a very attractive work environment for people who need to tend to children, parents, or other family members in need.
- Family businesses tend to operate more ethically. In fact, many family businesses believe that their ethical standards are more stringent than those of their competitors. In addition, family businesses are often deeply embedded in their communities, and this proximity is seen as an important factor that increases the likelihood of ethical decision making and moral behavior. As members of the local community, any ethical problems with a family business will be quickly visible.
- Family businesses also exhibit more social responsibility than their competitors. This has been attributed to their concern about image and local reputation as well as their closeness to the community.
- Family businesses may incur lower costs because of the greater willingness of family members to make financial sacrifices for the sake of the business. Accepting lower pay than they would get elsewhere to help the business in the longer term or deferring wages in a cash-flow crisis are examples of family altruistic behavior.
- Family businesses, in general, have greater independence of action because they have less (or no) pressure from the stock market and less (or no) takeover risk.

WEAKNESS

As attractive as family businesses are on many fronts, they have the following disadvantages:

- Family businesses tend to be stable organizations. Although this is a good thing in many instances, stability can also make it difficult to change. A new, younger family member coming into the business will find tradition and structure. Changing that is not simple. The key to changing a family business lies in defining tradition in terms of the company's core values, not in specific ways of doing things.
- Family closeness can lead to sibling rivalry or problems when both the parent and the child want control. By the third or fourth generation, with many cousins possibly sharing ownership, governance can become very complicated.
- There may be times when the interests of a family member conflict with the interests of the business. One family member may want to expand the business, but other family members may not share this person's desire. The needs of the business are not in sync with the needs of the family.
- Family ties have a downside. Family members will frequently be expected to work harder, make more of a commitment, and get paid less than other employees in the business.
- Family business owners may automatically promote someone from the family or give family members a job even if they do not have adequate skills for the job. A nonfamily employee may be better qualified. This can cause dissension and resentment among other employees.
- Relationships between parents and children or among siblings have a tendency to deteriorate due to communication problems. —This dysfunctional behavior can result in judgments, criticism and lack of support.
- The family business may be a breeding ground for jealousies, resentment, anger, and sabotage. Family problems may spill over into the workplace.
- The business may be plagued with managerial incompetence, the lack of exposure to other businesses, and the inability to separate family and work.
- Some family businesses may have difficulty attracting and keeping highly qualified managers. —Qualified managers may avoid family firms due to the exclusive succession, limited potential for professional growth, lack of perceived professionalism, and limitations on wealth transfer. Succession refers to passing the business to the next generation.

- Family businesses have limited sources of external capital because they tend to avoid sharing equity with nonfamily members. Having less access to capital markets may curtail growth.

- Not all children of owner-managers may want to join the business. According to one study, 80 percent of those who did not work in the family business did not intend to go into the business.

THREATS

Indian family businesses enjoy various advantages due to their inherent characteristics and a social culture that supports their structures. However, these advantages can be destroyed if the family is not united; as the family grows, the challenge is to keep a sense of unity. These are a set of typical challenges that Indian family businesses face today:

1. The Next Generation

The greatest challenge concerns the gap between family generations: A business founder is used to doing everything himself. Thus developed the unique culture of the present Indian family business: Inward-looking, owner centric, smaller scale, with a restricted perspective, and conservative mindset. This culture eventually becomes a hurdle in absorbing 'outsiders'. The same culture also poses a serious challenge in absorbing the next generation family members: Different generations, seeing the world differently are supposed to work together. It can be a difficult thing as the young generation is often in a hurry and has big ambitions, while their elders are more conservative and skeptical. The gap keeps on getting wider and wider. When conflict escalates between fathers and sons it is often the mother, who takes the role of CEO (Chief Emotional Officer). This is a common story in many Indian family businesses.

2. Attracting and Retaining Non-family Employees

Another possible challenge is non-family employees joining the family firm: The culture, which has solidified over time, becomes a barrier for accepting 'outsiders'. Business owners are often at a loss as to how much authority a non-family employee should be able to attain. In most Indian family businesses stakes are high: It is not easy to put their own destiny in the hands of non-family employees. Having founded the business, the owner is used to having insight into all aspects of his business. Allowing the same insight to an outsider can be hard. On the other hand non-family employees may also have difficulties in adjusting to the family business culture. They are used to structured corporate environments. In family businesses that structure may be missing. It is important that time is bestowed on new professionals so they can settle. Many Indian family business owners end up selecting non-family employees based on their performance in the corporate world without paying much attention to their 'fit' with their own firm's culture. They forget to spend time in facilitating the settling down process.

3. Women of the Family Joining the Family Business

Indian family businesses are still largely male dominated. The role of women in business and employing women is largely accepted and encouraged in India. However, when it comes to hiring women in the family business, there are reservations. Within the Indian social context of business families, bringing up the children is considered primarily a responsibility of the mother. Thus, whenever the issue of women in the family business is raised, it is subject to her ability to balance between her duties at home and her duties at work. However, as more and more women are highly educated, they are demanding a say in the family business. The traditional family model is still disapproving of it, yet increasingly it will have to respond to these demands. It is only reasonable for family businesses to tap into this huge source of talent.

OPPURTUNITY

In the race of survival, the families with a vision and a desire to continue their businesses across generations have to take measures to manage their businesses professionally while keeping their family ties stronger. When the family members have a common vision, well defined roles, open communication, and transparent systems of operations then the business can survive any test of time.

Easier said than done, it is difficult for the families to align goals and have an open dialogue among themselves. As a family business advisor, I work with the families to develop family governance and guide them through the process of professionalization with an unbiased, rational approach. By inculcating family governance, the roles and goals of the owner-managers are defined, their performances are evaluated, family's welfare and wealth management issues are addressed, and the younger generation members are trained for leadership. Indian family businesses are going through a challenging yet exiting time. The change factors are making family businesses reevaluate their vision and refix the priorities. Family and business, two sides of a coin, are being redefined in the new millennium. The threats and challenges of family businesses are still outweighed by the entrepreneurial zest, family values and culture. There is no doubt that the family businesses are taking up the challenges and will thrive for a long time as ever.

INDIA'S TOP FAMILY RUN BUSINESSES

1. Reliance Industries

Founded by Dhirubhai Ambani in 1966 as Reliance Commercial Corporation, Reliance industries is the largest private sector conglomerate company in India. The company was divided between the founder's two sons, Mukesh Ambani and Anil Ambani in 2006. In September 2008, Reliance Industries was the only Indian firm featured in the Forbes's list of "world's 100 most respected companies". In 2010, the company occupied the 13th position in the Platts Top 250 Global Energy Company Rankings. However the company's petrochemicals, refining, oil and gas-related operations form the core of its business, other segments of the company include textiles, retail business, telecommunications, and special economic zone (SEZ) development. Reliance Retail has moved into the fresh food market as Reliance Fresh. Almost 23,365 employees work in the Reliance industries.

2. Tata Consultancy services

Top IT exporter Tata Consultancy Services (TCS) comes second in the list and the company belongs to the most powerful and well-known family in India- the Tatas. Originally a priestly family in Navsari, they have been active in industry and philanthropy since nineteenth century. The Tata Group, founded by Jamsetji Tata, is one of the largest private employers in India. It began as the "Tata Computer Centre", for the company Tata Group whose main business was to provide computer services to other group companies. One of the company's' first assignments was to provide punch card services to its sister concern, Tata Steel (then TISCO). It later bagged the country's first software project, the Inter-Branch Reconciliation System (IBRS) for the Central Bank of India. In 1981, Jamsedji Tata stepped down as Tata Industries chairman, naming Ratan Tata as his successor. The company also provided bureau services to Unit Trust of India, thus becoming one of the first companies to offer BPO services. The Tata Family was one of the first to embrace changes in the 20th century entering the service industry with Tata Consultancy Services in 1968.

3. Bharati Airtel

Bharti Airtel popularly known as Airtel was founded by Sunil Bharti Mittal in 1995. It is an Indian telecommunications company that operates in 20 countries across South Asia, Africa and the Channel Islands. It operates a GSM network in many countries, providing 2G or 3G services depending upon the country of operation. Airtel is the fifth largest telecom operator in the world with about 230.8 million subscribers across 19 countries at the end of June 2011. The company is the largest cellular service provider in India, with over 171.85 million subscribers as of August 2011. Airtel is the 3rd largest in-country mobile operator by subscriber base, behind China Mobile and China Unicom. The company has its headquarters in New Delhi. Its main products are fixed-line and mobile telephony, broadband and fixed-line internet services, digital television, IPTV and network services. The company recently announced that Shravin Bharti Mittal, 23, one of twin sons of Sunil Bharti Mittal, is the manager of Bharti's international operations in Africa. Sunil and his brothers own 32 per cent of the company and are therefore worth something like Rs 20,000 crore.

4. Wipro

Headquartered in Bangalore, Wipro technologies is a global information technology services company which was founded by M.H. Hasham Premji in 1945. After M.H Hasan Premji's sudden death, his son Azim Premji had to leave Stanford University to take care of the company which he struggled to convert it into Wipro technologies. Recently Rishad Premji son of Azim Premji is promoted as the Vice President of Wipro. Wipro provides outsourced research and development, infrastructure outsourcing, business process outsourcing (BPO) and business consulting services. The company operates in three divisions: IT Services, IT Products, Consumer Care and Lighting. According to an annual survey conducted by Brand Finance and The Economic Times in 2010, Wipro is 9th most valuable brand in India. Azim Premji is the chairman of the company.

5. Jindal Group

Jindal Group was founded in 1952 by OP Jindal. After OP jindal's death in 2005 in a helicopter crash much of his assets were transferred to his wife, Savitri Jindal, the widow of OP jindal. She was ranked as the 19th richest Indian person by Forbes. Naveen Jindal is the Managing Director of Jindal Steel and Power limited. Naveen's elder brother Sajjan Jindal is currently the head of ASSOCHAM, an influential body of the chambers of commerce, and the head of JSW Group, part of O.P. Jindal Group. The company manufactures and sells sponge iron, mild steel slabs, ferro chrome, iron ore, mild steel, structural, hot rolled plates and coils and coal based sponge iron plant. Jindal steel and power limited is also engaged in power generation. Jindal Group has manufacturing outfits across India, US and Indonesia offices across the globe.

CONCLUSION

The Indian business landscape has started expanding fast. With the involvement of the older generation alone, such growth is unthinkable. While the parent generation needs to accept this, the next generation has to learn to appreciate their parents' wisdom and understand that there is no substitute for hard work. The solution to these challenges requires an understanding of the family business dynamics and a separation of people from problems. Family business members should learn that no one is wrong but that each generation has a different culture. Once families learn about these cultures and understand the need to appreciate different perspectives, whether young or old, they will be able to harmoniously work with professionals as well as across generations. Thus, if family businesses can manage these dynamics, they will be better placed to reap the benefits of the great range of opportunities in the Indian economy and beyond.

REFERENCE

- [1]. Carlock, Randel S; Manfred Kets de Vries and Elizabeth Florent-Treacy (2007). "Family Business". International Encyclopedia of Organizational Studies.
- [2]. Van der Heyden, Ludo; Blondel, Christine and Carlock, Randel S. (2005). "Fair Process: Striving for Justice in the Family Firm". *Family Business Review*. XVIII (1).
- [3]. ALDRICH, H. E., and CUFF, J. E. (2003). "The Pervasive Effects on Entrepreneurship: Embeddedness Perspective". *Journal of Business Venturing*, 18/5: 573-96.
- [4]. Aldrich, H.E., and J. E. Cliff.(2003) The Pervasive Effects of Family on Entrepreneurship: Towards a Family Embeddedness Perspective. *Journal of Business Venturing* 18(5):573-596.
- [5]. Allio, M.K. (2004) Family Businesses: Their Virtues, Vices, and Strategic Path, Strategy and Leadership, 32(4), 24-33.
- [6]. AMATORI, E, and BRIOSCHI, E (1997). "Le grandi imprese private: famiglie e coalizioni", in F. Barca (ed.), *Storia del capitalismo italiano*. Roma: Donzelli.--and Cmu, A. (1999). *Impresa e industria in Italia dal' Unitil ad oggi*. Venice: Marsilio. AMSDEN, A. (1986). *Asias Next Giant*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- [7]. ANONYMOUS REPoRT (2003). "Family Businesses Dominate: International Family Enterprise

Research Academy (IFERA)". Family Business Review, 16/4: 233-50.

- [8]. ARNOLDUS, D. (2002). Family, Firm and Strategy: Six Dutch Family Firms in the Food Industry, 1880-1970. Amsterdam: Aksant Akademik Publishers.
- [9]. Aronoff, C. E. (1998) Mega trends in Family Business. Family Business Review 11(3) 181-186.
- [10]. ASTRACHAN, J. H., and SHANKER, M. C (2003). "Family Businesses' Contribution to the US economy: A Closer Look": Family Business Review, 16/3: 150-67.
- [11]. Astrachan, J.H., and M. C. Shanker (2003) Family Businesses Contribution to the US Economy: A Closer Look. Family Business Review 16(3):211-219.